

The Relevance of Animal Farm : Unmasking Power, Language, and Lessons for Today's Society

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Abstract

Literature as a part of humanities mirrors both the ugly and the beautiful, the sordid and the noble. It not only broadens one's perspective but also makes us empathize with others by allowing readers to understand the struggles and viewpoints of others. It makes us learn from experiences of the characters portrayed and identify and navigate life's complex problems. George Orwell's *Animal Farm* is a profound novel that describes the mechanisms of propaganda, the rise of dictatorships, and the betrayal of revolutionary ideals. This paper explores the relevance of *Animal Farm* in modern times, highlighting how Orwell's insights into media manipulation and political control remain pertinent decades after its 1945 publication. Through the allegory of farm animals, Orwell vividly portrays the nature of corruption and the vulnerability of the common people to dictatorship. This paper draws parallels between the novel's themes and contemporary political realities. It underscores *Animal Farm* as a timeless cautionary tale that warns against the dangers of unchecked power.

Keywords

Dictatorship, Power, Corruption, Control, Propoganda, Freedom.

Introduction

Literature reflects realities, attitudes, and complexities of society. George Orwell's *Animal Farm*, published in 1945, stands as a powerful allegory highlighting power and corruption. It illustrates how revolutions that begin with noble intentions can be weakened and distorted. Orwell's *Animal Farm*, a direct allegory of the Russian Revolution, of 1917 and the rise of Stalinism. The shift from idealism to tyranny is captured by the novel and it mirrors the historical betrayal of revolutionary principles by Stalin and his followers. Through vividly drawn animal characters, Orwell depicts universal human traits—greed, power hunger, complacency, and the cyclical nature of oppression. Although, Orwell wrote *Animal Farm* primarily as an allegory of the 1917 Russian Revolution and its tragic aftermath, his novel is still relevant and serves as a broader critique of all failed revolutions. Orwell's reflections extended beyond Russia to include revolutions such as the French Revolution and the Spanish Civil War. The character of Napoleon, who becomes a ruthless despot on animal farm, is inspired by Napoleon Bonaparte, a key figure in the French Revolution. Orwell's choice to cast his story as a fable, using animals as characters, granted him the freedom to depict the brutalities committed during revolutionary upheavals while creating a timeless narrative. He captured how revolutions that started with high idealism turn sour through corrupting influence of power.

Objective of study

The objective of this study is to demonstrate the relevance of George Orwell's *Animal Farm* in contemporary times and how its themes and techniques are pertinent in the present turbulent times. The study examines Orwell's portrayal of the distortion of language and manipulation of facts and the tactics commonly employed by modern politicians to influence public opinion and promote their own interests. By analyzing *Animal Farm*, this research aims to highlight the similarities between past events depicted in the novel and the current political climate. It seeks to delineate how *Animal Farm* can be utilized within the broader field of literature and humanities to deepen our understanding of the psychology and motivations behind totalitarian mindsets. It seeks to demonstrate how literature serves as a powerful tool for recognizing and resisting the misuse of language and propaganda techniques by those in power. The paper underscores the importance of being vigilant about language manipulation and teaching readers to identify deceptive political rhetoric. This research intends to reaffirm the value of *Animal Farm* as a significant literary work as it equips us to analyze and challenge the distortion of facts in political discourse. The objective is not only to appreciate the novel's literary merit but also to make readers aware of the ongoing relevance of its themes so that they can resist manipulation and uphold truth in society.

Review of Literature

The existing literature on *Animal Farm* highlights the deft use of satire by George Orwell to expose the fake and brutal world of politics. The use of animal fable to bring out failure of totalitarian regimes and betrayal of masses is adroitly delineated. Scholars have also noted that propaganda machines such as Squealer have been used since times immemorial. Manipulation becomes a tool in the hands of corrupt rulers to distort facts for their benefit. To sniff out any protest mechanism and to instill loyalty among animals, slogans, songs and patriotic marches are organized. Researchers have drawn attention to use of allegory by Orwell to call attention to atrocities committed in Russian Revolution. They have also highlighted the failure of erstwhile revolutions and betrayal of

original manifesto as propounded by the precursors of the revolution such as Lenin in the Russian Revolution. Use of concepts such as media manipulation, political rhetoric, use of language to control and manipulate facts, societal control and misuse of power have also been noted by scholars. They also affirm *Animal Farm* as a timeless cautionary work that warns against the danger of allowing unchallenged authority to mould the truth and subjugate the people.

Main Text

Animal Farm portrays a farm where animals inspired by the philosophy of Animalism, propounded by Old Major, seek freedom and equality. After overthrowing their human oppressors, the pigs, especially Snowball and Napoleon, rise as leaders who educate and guide the animals according to the Seven Commandments of Animalism. At first, the revolution appears successful, with animals celebrating their newfound freedom and working for the common good. They engage in the same agricultural labour as humans once did, such as harvesting crops and caring for milk cows, symbolizing their aspiration toward self-sufficiency and equality.

Initially, the rebellion appears to bring hope: "All animals are equal"¹ (Orwell 17) and they celebrate their triumphs with enthusiasm. The animals even begin building a windmill, which symbolizes their strength and hope for a better future: "The windmill, which was supposed to work for all, was a symbol of power and progress"² (Orwell 53). However, as the pigs, particularly Napoleon, consolidate power, the windmill transforms from a tool for collective benefit into a means of exploitation, used to generate profit for the ruling elite. "The windmill, however, had not after all been used for generating power. It was used for milling corn, and brought in a handsome money profit."³(Orwell 88)

This reflects how scientific inventions and progress, though created for societal advancement, can be co-opted by the rich and powerful to serve their interests rather than those of the people. Early signs of corruption emerge when the pigs begin to monopolize education and privileges. Initially, the pigs consume the farm's milk and apples, justifying this as necessary for their well-being to lead and protect the farm. Over time, this small corruption escalates as the pigs increasingly resemble the human oppressors they replaced. The famous maxim "Four legs good, two legs bad"⁴ (Orwell 23) transforms into "Four legs good, two legs better,"⁵ (Orwell 92) signaling the pigs' betrayal of original revolutionary ideals.

The pigs introduce concepts akin to money and commerce, despite the revolution's initial rejection of such systems. They abandon the ban on alcohol, indulging in luxuries reminiscent of human excess. Under Napoleon's dictatorship, the farm becomes a totalitarian state with the use of fear, embodied by his ferocious dogs, to suppress dissent. The tragic fate of Boxer, the loyal workhorse who is sold off under false pretences despite his unquestioning devotion, starkly symbolizes the exploitation inherent in corrupt regimes.

Animal Farm is bitter commentary on society's customs, power structures, and culture. Orwell's novel acts as a warning about the dangers of unchecked power and the ease with which revolutions fail when the common people remain apathetic or are manipulated through propaganda. The animals' poor memory and gullibility, manipulated by Squealer's changing narratives, reflect how misinformation can perpetuate oppression. Squealer, the pig who functions as Napoleon's propagandist, exemplifies how language and communication are distorted to control and deceive the masses. He claims that the pigs' consumption of milk and apples is necessary because: "Milk and apples (this has been proved by Science, comrades) contain substances absolutely necessary to the well-being of a pig. We pigs are brainworkers"⁶ (Orwell 24).

This pseudo-scientific justification is designed to blind the other animals to inequality by appealing to their trust in science and reason. Throughout the novel, whenever the animals seek the truth, Squealer intervenes to manipulate reality and present it in a way that suits the pigs' interests. The pigs justify their luxury and indulgence even as the others suffer, repeatedly altering the Seven Commandments to fit their changing rules. Squealer explains away these changes, persuading the animals through lies and rhetoric: "No animal shall drink alcohol"⁷ (Orwell 17) became "No animal shall drink alcohol to excess"⁸(Orwell 75) after the pigs began drinking and "All animals are equal"⁹ (Orwell 17) eventually twisted to "All animals are equal, but some animals are more equal than others"¹⁰ (Orwell 92). When Boxer is taken away, Squealer spreads false reports claiming he is receiving the best care: "I was at his bedside at the very last," said Squealer, 'and those were his very last words, comrades. "Napoleon is always right!"¹¹ (Orwell 85). This lie is part of the ongoing manipulation to maintain control over the farm.

Orwell's *Animal Farm* thus reveals the mechanisms through which propaganda sustains dictatorships and language is weaponized to mislead. Truth is bent to justify privilege, and loyalty is exploited until betrayal occurs. Written during a time when many idealized Soviet Russia, Orwell's novel courageously exposed the dark realities behind such regimes and remains a timeless warning about the fragility of freedom when vigilance fails. At first, the pigs in *Animal Farm* appear almost comical in their arrogance and selfishness, but as the story unfolds, their cruelty and abuse of power become shocking. Their transformation culminates in their indistinguishability from the human oppressors they replaced. Orwell writes: "The creatures outside looked from pig to man, and from

man to pig, and from pig to man again; but already it was impossible to say which was which"¹² (Orwell 97). This chilling moment reflects how power corrupts absolutely and how revolutionary leaders can become tyrants themselves.

Orwell evokes sympathy particularly for Boxer, the hardworking and loyal cart-horse who embodies dedication and faith in the cause, whose slogan was, "I will work harder!"¹³(Orwell 50) and "Napoleon is always right"¹⁴(Orwell 56). Yet, Boxer is ultimately betrayed and callously sold by the ruling pigs when he is no longer useful and acquire money to buy whiskey after selling him. It is extreme betrayal on the part of pigs. The animals are misled to believe Boxer received medical care, while in truth he was sent to a slaughter house. Snowball, one of the more idealistic pigs, is a devoted believer in Animalism. He works tirelessly to educate the animals and promote equality, but he becomes a scapegoat for Napoleon's corrupt regime. This tactic mirrors the corrupt politicians use of scapegoats and propaganda to hide their crimes and maintain control.

The novel vividly illustrates how power corrupts; the initial commandments of Animalism are gradually altered to justify the pigs' increasing privileges. The famous line, "Four legs good, two legs better"¹⁵(Orwell 92) signifies the complete betrayal of the revolution's core ideals. The pigs begin living like humans, drinking alcohol, and indulging in luxuries, completely abandoning the principles they once espoused. Napoleon's reign is marked by oppression, manipulation, and violence, exemplified by the ruthless use of dogs as enforcers and the tragic betrayal of Boxer. "But the luxuries of which Snowball had once taught the animals to dream, the stalls with electric lights and hot and cold water, and the three-day week, were no longer talked about. Napoleon had denounced such ideas as contrary to the spirit of Animalism."¹⁶ (Orwell 88)

Orwell's *Animal Farm* serves as a poignant warning to the common people. If they remain naive, distracted, or silenced by propaganda—as the animals are by Squealer's constant revisions of the truth—they become complicit in their own oppression. Orwell writes, "The animals believed every word of it... They were thoroughly convinced that Snowball was a traitor"¹⁷ (Orwell 37). The novel urges vigilance and critical thinking, emphasizing that only through alertness and collective resistance can tyranny be prevented.

Conclusion

In conclusion, *Animal Farm* is not just an allegory of the Russian Revolution but a universal reflection on human nature's susceptibility to corruption. It warns that revolutions fail when power is centralized and when the masses do not question authority or propaganda. As Orwell's animals demonstrate, the denial of freedom and dignity ultimately arises when the common people allow dictators to reshape truth and history to serve their ends. George Orwell was deeply committed to political writing had a desire to expose the injustices inflicted by governments and the lies propagated by those in power. He was concerned about the growing tolerance and even admiration for dictatorship in many democratic countries and wanted to reveal the harsh realities behind such regimes. Orwell intended *Animal Farm* to challenge readers to think critically about right and wrong, and to debunk myths surrounding Soviet socialism. It shows that denial of education, manipulation of truth, and centralization of power inevitably lead to societal decay. *Animal Farm* serves both as a warning and a call to vigilance for contemporary societies, emphasizing the necessity of critical thinking and resistance to deceptive rhetoric. Its portrayal of the common masses' vulnerability and the corrupting influence of authoritative leadership holds vital lessons on safeguarding democracy and human dignity, making Orwell's work as relevant today as when it was first published.

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